

THE PRINCIPLE OF TOLERANCE IN THE IDEOSPHERE OF NEW UZBEKISTAN'S DEMOCRATIC SOCIETY

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Annotation: This article delves into the critical topics of ensuring security, fostering harmony among diverse ethnic groups, and promoting religious tolerance within the ideosphere of New Uzbekistan. It also examines the importance of implementing a well-considered, mutually advantageous, and pragmatic foreign policy. Moreover, the piece studies the extensive reforms designed to enhance civic peace, interethnic understanding, and interfaith harmony in Uzbekistan.

Key words: ideosphere, religion, tolerance, spirituality, culture, society, identity, development, tradition, resolution.

The role of Islamic culture and enlightenment was particularly important in the restoration of the religious and spiritual foundations of the society's ideosphere. Because the noble ideas of our holy Islam religion have a deep scientific-philosophical basis, it is a religion of goodness, peace, kindness, and in terms of content, it calls for truthfulness and purity. Also, religion was an important step in bringing people to tolerance, raising the ideosphere of society, and bringing them to spiritual maturity. In the process of this renewal, the historical memory of our people was restored and it helped them realize their identity. As a result, holy places, shrines, mosques and madrassas in the country were renovated.

These reforms in improving the ideosphere of the society were implemented by the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 14, 2017 "On measures to establish the Imam Termizi International Research Center" [1], the Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 2, 2017 "On the organization of the activities of the Center of Islamic Culture in Uzbekistan under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan" [2], on September 6, 2017, the opening of the newly established Bukhara Higher Madrasa in the Bahauddin Naqshband complex in Bukhara, on November 10, 2017, the Bahauddin Naqshband School of Sufism was opened at the Mir Arab Higher Madrasah located in Bukhara region, in 2020, we can see Bukhara being recognized as the capital of Islamic culture.

We are observing that transferring Islam from abroad is appropriate due to the restoration of Islamic values and spirituality in society's ideosphere. However, it is important to ensure that Islam is not politicized within the democratic management system of the state. Considering the presence of representatives of various religions in our society, the Constitution of Uzbekistan and the Law "On Freedom of Conscience and Religious Organizations" prevent the generalization of Islam in our country. People of science and culture such as I. Kalantarov, Yu. Ishakov, L.Aronova, M.Koziyev, B.Pinjasov, N. Mallayev, composers such as M.Leviyev, S. Yudakov, artists such as Yu. Yelizarov, public artists of Uzbekistan B.Davidova, I.Oqilov, M. Yakubova and others were representatives of different nationalities born in our country. This is evidenced by the fact that they made a great contribution to the development of society, in particular, to its ideosphere [3].

The implementation of the Strategy of Actions will infuse new strength into the determined efforts to reform and modernize the Republic of Uzbekistan, establish a legal democratic state based on a developed market economy, build a strong civil society, uphold the rule of law, ensure security and law enforcement, safeguard state borders, and promote interethnic harmony and religious tolerance in society. This will further elevate the ideosphere of the society.

While national-ethnic relations are becoming complex in some countries and cases of discrimination against minority groups are observed in certain states, Uzbekistan, where people live harmoniously and cooperatively like members of a single family, is undoubtedly an example for other nations.

The head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his Address to the Oliy Majlis on December 28, 2018, states the following about this: "Uzbekistan is always faithful to its traditions in the field of inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance, and will never deviate from this path.

In our country, primary attention is paid to strengthening the atmosphere of mutual respect, friendship and harmony between representatives of different nationalities and religious confessions. This is our greatest treasure, and it is everyone's duty to protect and cherish it like the apple of our eye. As you know, recently the plenary session of the United Nations General Assembly adopted an important document - the resolution "Enlightenment and religious tolerance". The initiative to adopt this resolution was put forward by Uzbekistan at the 72nd session of the General Assembly in September 2017" [4].

On December 12, 2018, a special resolution called "Enlightenment and religious tolerance" was adopted at the plenary session of the UN General Assembly,

which occupies an important place in the ideosphere of society. The document drafted by Uzbekistan was unanimously supported by all UN member states. The adoption of the resolution was a practical expression of the initiative put forward by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the 72nd session of the UN General Assembly held in New York in September 2017 [5]. The head of our state noted that the main goal of the resolution proposed by Uzbekistan at the top of the UN is to “ensure everyone’s right to education, help to eliminate illiteracy and ignorance”. The document is aimed at “establishing tolerance and mutual respect, ensuring religious freedom, protecting the rights of believers, and helping to prevent their discrimination”. In order to implement this initiative, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Uzbekistan, in collaboration with several other agencies, undertook systematic efforts to draft the resolution text and negotiate it with all member states of the United Nations [5]. It is noteworthy that this resolution was not only unanimously supported by all member states of the United Nations but also adopted in co-authorship with more than 50 countries from North and Latin America, Asia, Africa, and other continents. This is a high recognition by the international community of the timeliness and merit of the initiative proposed by the leader of Uzbekistan. Among the co-authors are Azerbaijan, Algeria, Bahrain, Belarus, Ghana, Egypt, India, Kazakhstan, Canada, Qatar, Kyrgyzstan, Lebanon, Morocco, the UAE, Oman, Pakistan, South Korea, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, Sudan, Tajikistan, Thailand, Tunisia, Turkmenistan, the Philippines, Japan, and other countries. The document supports all international, regional, and national initiatives aimed at promoting harmony in religious and interethnic relations, as well as combating discrimination based on religion and beliefs against individuals. The reforms being carried out and the normative-legal documents being adopted in our country to strengthen interethnic relations all serve to advance the development of our Republic and to bolster stability within the country.

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